

THE NEED FOR A SOCIO-GEOGRAPHICAL APPROACH TO THE STUDY OF ETHNOECOLOGICAL CULTURE

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A complex approach is of particular importance in conducting ethnoecological research, because these studies have a natural and social nature at the same time. Although most of the problems waiting to be solved in the research are of a natural-ecological nature, the solution of socio-historical issues plays a major role in their solution. Therefore, in the research work, special attention is paid to the historical and ecological approaches that incorporate complex views [3, 4].

Today, the main indicators of the geocological scientific direction are considered to be the main indicators of the scientific direction of geocology, the amount of use and production of nature, the number of people, the number of natural resources. there is a need to monitor changes in indicators such as the scale of use, the amount of anthropogenic pressure on nature, ecological and ethno-ecological landscape balance in space and time [1, 2, 6]. This, in turn, shows the need for a historical approach along with an innovative approach to maintaining ecological balance.

The principles, types and form of territorial organization of the community in economic and social geography may change under the influence of various factors. V.A. Pulyarkin, on the example of the countries of the world, proved that this situation can be more clearly manifested in the process of using nature, including land resources [5, 7]. Analyzing based on these methodological bases, Yu.I.Ahmadaliev proposed to distinguish three types of regional organization of the use of natural resources in regional conditions. Based on the purpose of using nature, these types are conventionally called natural-organizational, commodity-targeted and program-targeted [7, 8].

We called the first type of use of nature based on the use of the natural resources of the region, which existed in the Fergana Valley until the end of the 19th century and

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the beginning of the 20th century, because the organizational aspects of the issue were not so developed during this period. In this type of territorial organization of the use of nature, relief, climate, soil characteristics, the closed position of the valley, as well as the national-ethnic characteristics, skills, skills and habits of the population are taken into account. This type is usually formed over a long historical period, and the skills, competences and experiences accumulated in it are based on a harmonious, balanced relationship with nature. Therefore, from an ecological point of view, this species is the most robust and is worth studying for this purpose.

If the interactions of the "Ethno-landscape-economy" system are placed in the form of "geotriens", it will be shown that the main burden falls on the economy, and that it is carried out in accordance with the landscape indicators in the territorial organization of the economy. It is shown that only the indicators of management that correspond to the landscape requirements of the ethnos are preserved as "skills-qualifications-traditions". With the development of "ethno-landscape-economy" relations, the amount of natural landscapes (biosphere) in any region decreases, and economic (technosphere) indicators begin to take its place [8].

As relations in the "ethno-landscape-economy" system improve, [9] the place of the first type is replaced by the commodity type of territorial organization of the next nature use. In this type, along with the natural possibilities of the region, subjective factors (for example, the increase in demand for commodity crops, the penetration of foreign ethnic groups into the landscape) are also taken into account. As a result, the natural landscape features of the region are changed more, the achievements of scientific and technical development are widely used. Although the economic efficiency is high, the ground is prepared for the emergence of geo-ecological problems. This species existed in the Fergana Valley from 1876 to 1991.

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